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THE LUBNY FIELD PHARMACY – THE FIRST PHARMACY IN THE LEFT-BANK UKRAINE

Початок аптечної справи на Лубениціні слід пов'язати з Мгарським монастирем. Після Полтавської битви 1709 р., російський цар Петро I зробив короточасну зупинку у Лубнах. Вигідне стратегічне положення міста, багатий рослинний світ та традиції Мгарського монастиря навели його на думку про заснування тут польової аптеки, яка могла б забезпечувати ліками війська, що охороняли південь держави. На підставі ретельного вивчення архівних документів, можна стверджувати, що Лубенська польова аптека була першою польовою аптекою на Лівобережній Україні та з часом стала центром розвитку аптечної справи і культивування лікарських рослин в цьому регіоні.

Ключові слова: аптека, Лубни.

Начало аптечного дела в Лубенском крае следует связывать с появлением Мгарского монастыря. После Полтавской битвы 1709 г., российский царь Петр I не надолго остановился в Лубнах. Выгодное стратегическое положение, богатый растительный мир, традиции Мгарского монастыря навели его на мысль об основании тут полевой аптеки для обеспечения лекарствами войск, которые охраняли южные рубежи страны. На основании тщательного изучения архивных документов, можно утверждать, что Лубенская полевая аптека была первой полевой аптекой на Левобережной Украине и со временем стала центром развития аптечного дела и культивирования лекарственных растений в этом регионе.

Ключевые слова: аптека, Лубны.

The Lubny pharmacy inherited traditions of the Mhar's monastery. After the Battle of Poltava in 1709, the Russian Tsar Peter I made a brief stay in Lubny. He noticed an advantageous strategic position of the city. Besides the rich flora and traditions of the Mhar's monastery suggested him an idea to establish a field pharmacy that could provide troops guarding the south of the state with medicines. Archival documents show that the Lubny field pharmacy was the first one on the Left-Bank Ukraine and eventually became the centre of pharmacy and cultivation of medicinal plants in the region. Traditions of the Lubny pharmaceutical industry were revived in the Soviet times.

Keywords: pharmacy, Lubny.

Introduction. Lubny is one of the oldest towns in our country. The history of Lubny foundation is associated with the name of the Kyivan Prince Volodymyr Svyatoslavych [1;2]. The beginning of the pharmaceutical business in Lubny is connected with the Mhar's monastery that was founded in 1619. The traditions of the Mhar's monastery were inherited by the first in the Left Bank Ukraine field pharmacy that was opened in 1733 by the Senate order.

Objective. There is a field pharmacy in Lubny. While studying, it became clear that the history of its origin is connected with interesting historical facts and even legends. The convenient strategic location, climate, rich flora of the region created favourable conditions for the establishment of a pharmacy; and these factors were decisive for its long existence and effective operation.

The aim of article: Based on the study of archival documents and research literature, we made an attempt to determine the date of foundation of the Lubny field pharmacy, that is

controversial in the scientific literature. Accurate information on the opening of the pharmacy, after the Lubny archive was destroyed in 1944 during the Second World War, is almost gone.

Materials and methods: research of preserved unique archive materials, study and analysis of scientific literature.

There is a quite common opinion that Peter I personally founded the Lubny pharmacy. As a rule, history books on the origin and development of medicine usually note that Peter I founded the State field pharmacy, botanical and pharmaceutical gardens for growing medicinal plants in Lubny [3; 4; 5].

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Various authors give different dates of the pharmacy foundation. An indisputable proof of the pharmacy operation in 1721 is a document given by a scientist F. F. Isaiev. It is a complaint of the owner of the house, which

from 1717 till 1767 is another documentary evidence to the fact that the Lubny pharmacy had already worked in 1721 [2]. It is a record of Ya. A. Markovych that states that the first pharmacist of the field pharmacy was Ivan Heiter.

Archival documents also prove the fact that in February, 1725, the peasant Taras “came back from Lubny and brought medicines from the pharmacy, 6 items, and it is necessary to pay 3 roubles 99 kopecks to the pharmacy” [4].

In 1736, a Special Government Commission inspecting the activities of Russian pharmacies held up the Lubny pharmacy as an example as the best one.

Thus, the found archival materials definitely confirm the fact that the Lubny field pharmacy was established during the life of Peter I, and the Senate's Decree of September 3, 1733 officially registered the existing pharmacy.

One can get interesting data on the pharmacy work from "catalogues", dated back to 1757. They indicated that the pharmacy nomenclature included a large group of medicines of the plant origin. In pure form, it made up 57.7% of the range of medicines in the pharmacy.

Medicines of the chemical origin in pure form formed only 8.7%; other medicaments were chemical mixtures of ingredients of the plant and animal origin. The pharmacy manufactured such compound pharmaceutical preparations as “Roman mush”, patches (lead, red, protective and stomach ones), essences (antiscorbutic, gastric, quinine, etc.), ointments, tinctures, waters [4].

Archival documents show that in a course of time the Lubny field pharmacy became the centre of pharmacy and cultivation of medicinal plants in Ukraine.

It is safe to say that if the supreme military authorities had not decided that it was cheaper to buy medicines abroad and not

initially housed the pharmacy, dated back to 1721 [4].

A personal diary of Yakov Andriyovych Markovych who lived in Lubny

eliminated “in April 18, 1862, the military pharmacy in Lubny with botanical gardens”, the development of pharmacy in Lubny would had continued.

In Soviet times, All-Union Institute of Medicinal Plants (VILR) of Ministry of Health of the USSR worked in Lubny. Along with the Station of Medicinal Plants there worked the Factory of Essential Oil Plants Processing [6:39]. Medicines with Lubny brand, manufactured in the Chemical-Pharmaceutical Factory, are known both in our country and abroad. In such a way, the business that was founded at the beginning of the 18th century in Lubny has continued to develop.

Conclusion. Based on a thorough study of archival documents, one could state the established assertion that the Lubny field pharmacy was founded by the Senate order in 1733 needs to be adjusted. The Lubny field pharmacy had begun its work much earlier, during the life of Peter I (1682-1725). Analysis of archived documents proves the opinion of Professor Ya. Chystovych that the Lubny pharmacy was one of the first two field pharmacies that “were founded in 1716”.

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Prospects for the further research: based on the study of archive documents we aim to find out the names of the first pharmacists, location and administrative organization of the pharmacy, the most spread illnesses at the time, and means of their treatment, nomenclature of medications, history of the foundation of the pharmaceutical botanical garden in the town of Lubny.

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